

CONNECTING RESEARCH,
ADVANCING KNOWLEDGE

DataCite: Getting Started

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Get Started

DataCite Members and Consortium Organizations that join DataCite can access DOI registration services. This quick start guide aims to cover the most important aspects of getting started with DataCite.

- Account Management
- DOI Registration
- Metadata
- FAQs and Resources

You can always contact us at support@datacite.org if you get stuck.

Account Management

About Fabrica

Fabrica is DataCite's web interface for DOI registration and account management.

You can log in here: <https://doi.datacite.org/>

You can reset the password here: <https://doi.datacite.org/reset>

Whether your organization is a Direct Member or part of a DataCite Consortium, it's important to remember you will have **two types of account**.

1. The Direct Member or Consortium Organization account - you only have one of these
2. The Repository account (s) - you can create multiple Repository accounts

Tip: The system email contact will receive the password reset so it's important to keep this contact information up to date!

1. Direct Member/Consortium Organization Account

Log in with your Member or Consortium Organization account **to manage Repository accounts and add/update contact information.**

The Member or Consortium Organization dashboard in Fabrica.

Example Member account

Info **Settings** Contacts Repositories Prefixes DOIs

 Set Password

 Update Member

Record created
January 29, 2021 at 08:03:41 UTC

Record last modified
January 9, 2023 at 13:15:15 UTC

Organization Information

Member ID
XYBW

Member Type
Direct Member

Tax Status
Non-Profit

2. Repository Account

Log in with your repository account to **create and manage DOIs and metadata.**

The Repository dashboard in Fabrica.

Example Repository

Info **Settings** Prefixes DOIs

 Set Password

 Update Repository

Repository ID
EXAMPLE.FGRGCF

System Email
support@datacite.org

Domain
*

Record created
February 19, 2020 at 09:37:06 UTC

Record last modified
January 9, 2023 at 10:09:13 UTC

Fabrica documentation:

1. The [Fabrica user guide](#) provides detailed descriptions of how to use the different features of the web interface.
2. The [Fabrica FAQ](#) provides quick answers to frequently asked questions.

The DataCite test environment is completely separate from the production environment. Use test like a sandbox for creating your first DOI or setting up an integration.

- **DOI Fabrica** (<https://doi.test.datacite.org>)
- **REST API** (<https://api.test.datacite.org>)
- **MDS API** (<https://mds.test.datacite.org>)

Test environment documentation:

1. The [testing guide](#) includes information about the test site and how to access.
2. The [test FAQ](#) highlights the main differences between test and production.

Access: Which account should I use?

TEST

Follow the exact same process in the TEST ENVIRONMENT with your TEST credentials! Test and production are completely separate environments.

DOI Fabrica

(<https://doi.test.datacite.org>)

REST API

(<https://api.test.datacite.org>)

MDS API

(<https://mds.test.datacite.org>)

START: Where do you want to access?

PRODUCTION

Which method do you want to use?

API:
REST (<https://api.datacite.org>)
MDS (<https://mds.datacite.org>)

FABRICA (web interface):
<https://doi.datacite.org>

What do you want to do?

Create/update a DOI

Create a Repository or update contact information

Yes

Is your organization a Direct Member?

No

Use your REPOSITORY account
e.g. OUBU.UYTRU

Use your MEMBER account
e.g. XYZX

I don't know?

contact: support@datacite.org

Use your CONSORTIUM ORGANIZATION account e.g. OIKJ

DOI Registration

There are 3 ways to register a DOI:

1. The Fabrica web interface provides two options for registering DOIs. The easiest option is the [form for DOI creation](#). There is also the [file upload option](#) which accepts metadata files in XML and other formats.
2. The APIs are for developers looking to build an integration and for anyone who wants to retrieve metadata. New users should use the REST API. A detailed guide for [using the REST API](#) is available as well as the [API reference](#).
3. Some organizations choose to register DOIs with a registered [integration from a DataCite Registered Service Provider](#).

Prefixes

A DOI prefix always starts with '10.' and continues with a number (e.g. '10.1234' or '10.20865'). The DOI prefix is used as a namespace so that DOIs are globally unique. Each Repository account must have a prefix to register DOIs.

10.5438/9te8-5h68

Suffixes

The easiest and recommended option is to use **a randomly generated suffix**. If you choose not to use this option, remember:

1. The DOI suffix must be unique within each prefix. The optimum length of a DOI suffix is 6–10 characters.
2. Only use a-z, 0-9 and - in a DOI suffix. Other characters might have special meaning or will be escaped. DOI suffixes are not case sensitive.
3. Avoid human-readable information in a DOI suffix because any meaning may change over time. Further advice on DOI suffixes.

You can generate a random suffix in both Fabrica and the API and your DOI will look something like this:

10.5438/9te8-5h68

Versioning

DOI metadata can be updated. This includes the content underlying the DOI, e.g. correcting small errors like typos or adding a new file. This means small changes don't always require a new DOI. Individual stewards need to determine which are major vs. minor versions.

Data Citation

Data Citation means references to data, in the same way researchers routinely provide a bibliographic reference to other scholarly resources. Data are often shared, but they are not often cited the same way as journal articles or other publications. Repositories can participate by including information about publications that cite the data in DOI metadata.

Metadata

The Metadata Schema

Everything you need to know about the DataCite Metadata Schema can be found here:

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

The detailed guide includes definitions and descriptions of every metadata property plus lots of examples. It is updated and maintained by the [Metadata Working Group](#).

FAQs & Resources

- Why can't I see the create DOI option?
 - Check [which account](#) you're using.
- I'm having problems logging into Fabrica?
 - Often due to [browser related issues](#).
- I'm not receiving the password reset?
 - Check the [system email contact](#).
- Can I delete or change a DOI created by accident?
 - It's not possible to [delete a DOI](#) once the DOI is in Registered or Findable state.
- Why is the URL I entered giving an error?
 - Check domain filter setting if the [URL of my DOI is not accepted](#).
- Why is an unauthorized error appearing?
 - The [403 or unauthorized message](#) received from an integration means the password or prefix is wrong.
- How can I activate the ORCID auto-update?
 - Follow the [ORCID auto-update](#) guide.

Important Resources

Support site: <https://support.datacite.org/>

Support email: support@datacite.org

DataCite Blog: <https://blog.datacite.org/>

DataCite on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/DataCiteChannel>

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